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EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND TEACHING COMPETENCY OF B.Ed. STUDENTS IN KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT

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Abstract

The investigator was conducted to study the Emotional intelligence and Teaching competency of B.Ed. students in Kanyakumari District. The investigator collected data from 330 student-teachers by stratified random sampling method. Emotional Intelligence scale and teaching competency scale were used as the main tools. The obtained results showed that there is low correlation between Emotional intelligence and Teaching competency of student teachers. The relationship between Emotional intelligence and Teaching competency was noted to be a significant low correlation.

Keywords: B.Ed Students; Teaching Competency; Emotional; Intelligence & Relationship.

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1. Introduction

Emotional Intelligence plays a vital role in all human beings to lead a well-balanced life in the society. Several studies have shown that, it has direct impact on the teacher's behavior working in an educational organizations and it is important for the success of their profession. Teachers are considered as the main pillars in the educational system .They are the moderators through which the knowledge can be transferred to the students who represent the foundation of the society. The teaching competency is one of the abilities needed for all teachers and this skill is really necessary for all the teachers.

2. Review of Related Literature

Nimavathi (2015) conducted a study on “emotional intelligence and self-esteem among B.Ed students”. The objectives were intended to study if there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and self-esteem among B.Ed students. Samples of 300 B.Ed students. Survey method was used in the study. Emotional intelligence scale developed and standardized by UpinDhār, SanjoyatPethe and Anukool Hyde (2002). The statistical technique used for mean, S.D, t-test and co- efficient of correlation were used. The major findings of the study, there are a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and self-esteem among B.Ed students.

Laxmi (2013) conduct a study on emotional intelligence, self-esteem and teaching competency of secondary student teachers. The objectives were intended to compare emotional intelligence, self-esteem and teaching competency of gender, religion, type of college. The survey method was used for the present study. The sample consisted of 552 trainees. Emotional intelligence scales validated by the investigator were used as the tool for the study. The statistical techniques used for mean, S.D, correlation and ANOVA. The findings showed that is a significant difference in emotional intelligence self-esteem and teaching competency between the gender religion and types of colleges.

3. Statement of the Problems

The investigator selected the problem as entitled as “*Emotional intelligence and Teaching competency of B.Ed. Students in Kanyakumari District*”.

4. Objectives of the Study

- To find out the correlation between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of B.Ed. students.
- To find out whether there is any difference in the emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., gender, locality and type of management.
- To find out whether there is any difference in the emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., religion and family income.
- To find out whether there is any difference in the teaching competency of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., gender locality, and type of management.
- To find whether there is any difference in the teaching competency of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., religion, and family income.

5. Hypotheses of the Study

- There is no significant correction between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of B.Ed. students.
- There is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., gender, locality and type of management.
- There is no significant difference in the emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., religion and family income.

- There is no significant difference in the teaching competency of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., gender, locality and type of management.
- There is no significant difference in the teaching competency of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., religion and family income.

6. Methodology

Method

The investigator adopted normative survey method of research to study the problem.

Population

The population of the present study was B.Ed. students of the various colleges located in Kanniyakumari District.

Sample

The sample of the present investigation included 330 B.Ed. students from selected colleges located in Kanniyakumari Districts.

Tools used

For the present study the investigator made use of

- Emotional intelligence scale developed and validated by the investigator (2016).
- Teaching competency scale(Amala doss Xavier,2009)

Statistical Techniques used

The collected data were analyzed by using statistical techniques like percentage analysis mean, standard deviation, correlation, t-test and ANOVA.

7. Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The study has been analyzed systematically and given in different tables.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant correlation exists between Emotional Intelligence and teaching competency of B.Ed students.

The correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching competency of B.Ed. students was found using correlation on a sample of 330 students.

Table 1: Data and results of correlation between Emotional intelligence and Teaching competency of B.Ed. students

Variables correlated	N	r	Verbal Interpretation	Level of Significant
Emotional intelligence and teaching competency	330	0.321	low correlation	0.01 level

Table 1 indicates that the Correlation between emotional intelligence and teaching competency obtained on a sample of 330 student teachers. Since the calculated ‘r’ value (0.321) is less than the table value 0.148 at 0.01 level, it is inferred that there is a significant low relation between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of student teachers. Therefore, on the basis of the results given in the Table 1. Hypothesis-1 which stated that, “There is no significant correlation exist between Emotional intelligence and Teaching competency of B.Ed. students”, was accepted.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in the Emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz, gender, locality and type of management.

The difference between gender, locality and type of management in their job satisfaction was found using t-test on a sample of 330 B.Ed. students.

Table 2: Data and results of t-test, Comparison of Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed. Student Teachers based on the demographic variables between Gender, Locality and Type of Management

S.No.	Emotional intelligence		N	Mean	S D	‘t’ value
1	Gender	Male	51	102.25	11.639	6.890 (S)
		Female	279	115.91	13.243	
2	Locality	Rural	243	111.61	13.749	4.936 (S)
		Urban	87	119.90	12.494	
3	Type of Management	Aided	102	116.94	12.422	2.776 (S)
		Self-finance	228	112.39	14.315	

NS-Significant, S-significant

Table 2 has shown that the obtained ‘t’ value for the variable emotional intelligence of the student teachers in terms of their gender (t=6.890), locality (t=4.936) and types of management (t=2.776) are greater than table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it can be inferred that the student teachers differ in their emotional intelligence with respect to the gender, locality and type of management. Therefore hypothesis 2 is not accepted.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence of B.Ed students with regard to the demographic variables viz., religion and family income.

The differences among religion and family income in their Emotional Intelligence was found using ANOVA on a sample of 330 B.Ed. students.

Table 3: Data and results of ANOVA, Comparison Emotional intelligence of B.Ed. Students based on the demographic variables religion and family income

S.No	Emotional intelligence		SS	DF	MS	F
1	Religion	Between Groups	6342.55	2	18.121	0.01 level (S)
		Within Groups	57221.342	327	174.989	
2	Income	Between Groups	2381.114	2	1190.557	6.363 (S)
		Within Groups	61182.283	327	187.102	

NS-Not Significant, S-significant

Table 3 has shown that the obtained 'F' value for the variable student teachers in terms of their religion and family income are greater than table value 3.00 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it can be inferred that the student teachers do differ in their emotional intelligence with respect to the religion and family income. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is not accepted.

Hypothesis 4:

There is no significant difference in the Teaching competency of B.Ed students with regard to the demographic variables viz., gender, locality and type of management.

The difference between gender, locality and type of management in their Teaching competency was found using t-test on a sample of 330 students.

Table 4: Data and results of t-test, Comparison of teaching competency of Student Teachers based on the demographic variables between gender, locality and type of Management

S.No.	Teaching competency		N	Mean	S D	't' value
1	Gender	Male	51	120.06	25.278	5.410 (S)
		Female	279	93.36	33.526	
2	Locality	Rural	243	105.56	33.001	7.902(S)
		Urban	87	74.95	24.498	
3	Type of Management	Aided	102	116.94	12.422	2.776(S)
		Self-finance	228	112.39	14.315	

NS-not significant, S-significant

Table 4 has shown that the obtained 't' value for the Teaching competency of student teachers in terms of gender (t=5.410), locality (t=7.902), type of management (2.776) is greater than table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it can be inferred that the student teachers differ in their teaching competency with respect to the gender, locality and type of management. Therefore, hypothesis 4 is not accepted.

Hypothesis 5:

There is no significant difference in the Teaching competency of B.Ed. students with regard to the demographic variables viz., religion and family income.

Table 5: Data and results of ANOVA, Comparison of teaching competency of Student teachers based on the demographic variables religion and family income

S.No.	Teaching competency		SS	Df	MS	F
1	Religion	Between Groups	1568.485	2	784.242	0.686 (NS)
		Within Groups	373587.967	327	1142.471	
2	Family income	Between Groups	5204.482	2	2602.241	2.300 (NS)
		Within Groups	369951.969	327	1131.352	

NS-non significant, S-significant

Table 5 has shown that the obtained ‘F’ value of the student teachers in terms of their religion (f=0.686) and family income (f=2.300) are less than table value 3.00 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence it can be inferred that the student teachers differ in their teaching competency with respect to the religion, and income. Therefore, hypothesis 5 is accepted.

8. Findings of the Study

- There exists a low correlation between emotional intelligence and Teaching competency of student teachers.
- There is significant difference between the emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with respect to gender, location and type of management.
- There is significant difference between the emotional intelligence of B.Ed. students with respect to religion and family income.
- There is significant difference between the teaching competency of B.Ed. students with respect to gender, location and type of management.
- There is no significant difference the teaching competency of B.Ed. students with respect to religion and family income.

Conclusion

Emotional intelligence is necessity for every B.Ed. teacher trainees. If we can develop the emotional competencies of the B.Ed. teacher trainees, which in turn help them to develop the same among their students inspirational subjects like art, literature, poetry and music help in developing an appreciation of the beautiful and sublime emotions in life. They should be included in the teacher education curriculum. Teaching competency in teaching can be developed in teachers by means of emotional intelligence. It is therefore most important for student teacher to develop the emotional intelligence to become a perfect teacher. The concept of emotional intelligence may be incorporated in the teacher education curriculum to revitalize teacher education programs.

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